

An Indian female Morvan patient with LGI1 and CASPR2 antibodies: A Rare case report

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ABSTRACT

Background: Morvan syndrome is a rare autoimmune neurological disorder linked to antibodies directed against two voltage-gated potassium channel complex proteins, Contactin-Associated Protein-Like 2 and Leucine-Rich Glioma-Inactivated Protein 1. Dual positivity for both antibodies is extremely rare. We report a case of an 18-year-old female diagnosed with MoS showing seropositivity for both antibodies. **Case Presentation:** An 18-year-old female presented to the General Medicine department with acute lower back pain radiating to both lower limbs. She had been asymptomatic before 20 days, after which she developed gradually progressive low back pain with bilateral sciatica, accompanied by insomnia of the same duration. A diagnosis of Morvan syndrome was made based on clinical features and the detection of Contactin-Associated Protein-Like 2 and Leucine-Rich Glioma-Inactivated Protein 1 antibodies in her serum. She was treated with intravenous methylprednisolone followed by oral prednisone, along with five sessions of plasmapheresis and supportive medications. Over the next several days, her symptoms of myokymia and insomnia showed significant improvement, and her overall condition was better at the time of discharge. **Conclusion:** This case describes the clinical features of a female patient with Morvan syndrome showing both antibody positivity. It further supports that non-paraneoplastic Morvan syndrome cases can respond effectively to immunotherapy.

Keywords: Morvan syndrome, LGI1, CASPR2, plasmapheresis, VGKC antibodies, female patient

INTRODUCTION

Morvan syndrome (MoS) is an uncommon and intricate neurological disorder characterised by excessive excitability of the nervous system. It was first described by Dr Augustine Marie Morvan, a French physician, in April 1890 in La Gazette Hebdomadaire de Médecine et de Chirurgie. He initially termed the condition la chorée fibrillaire (fibrillary chorea), which is now known eponymously as Morvan syndrome.¹ Morvan syndrome, also called Morvan's fibrillary chorea, represents a rare paraneoplastic neurological condition originally identified in 1890. It manifests with a triad of central nervous system (CNS) involvement, peripheral nerve hyperexcitability, and autonomic nervous system (ANS) dysfunction.²

ETIOLOGY

i. Anti-VGKC Complex Antibodies

Anti-Contactin-Associated Protein-Like 2 (CASPR2): In 1999, researchers first identified a novel autoantibody belonging to the neuexin superfamily an axonal transmembrane protein known as anti-contactin-associated protein-like 2 (CASPR2). To date, roughly 60 cases of CASPR2-associated MoS have been reported in the French medical literature, while two English-language case series have described a total of 43 patients.¹

Leucine-Rich Glioma Inactivated 1 (LGI1) Protein & Netrin-1: In certain cases, antibodies targeting leucine-rich glioma inactivated 1 (LGI1) protein comprising receptor subunits such as epitempin, DCC as well as antibodies against the netrin-1 receptor have been linked to the disease process in both MoS and

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

limbic encephalitis.^{1,11} Netrin-1 is involved in angiogenesis, inflammation, tissue remodelling, and tumorigenesis; antibodies directed at its receptor have been associated with neuromyotonia in myasthenia gravis (MG) patients with thymoma.^{1,11} Some individuals also develop antibodies against another VGKC-complex antigen, contactin-2.^{1,12} MoS is considered an autoimmune neurological disorder within the spectrum of diseases associated with antibodies against voltage-gated potassium channel (VGKC) complex proteins. These antibodies contribute to the pathophysiology of MoS, acquired neuromyotonia (Isaac syndrome), limbic encephalitis, and faciobrachial dystonic seizures.^{1,10}

ii. Paraneoplastic Syndrome

Morvan syndrome has long been recognised as a paraneoplastic entity, most frequently linked with thymoma. Several reports describe MoS occurring alongside myasthenia gravis in patients with thymoma. In such cases, tumour cells express neuronal antigens, prompting the immune system to produce autoantibodies that subsequently attack components of the nervous system.^{1,10}

EPIDEMIOLOGY

According to Orphanet (accessed January 2024), MoS is an extremely rare, life-threatening, acquired neurological disorder with an incidence of fewer than one case per million. It is marked by neuromyotonia, dysautonomia, and encephalopathy accompanied by severe insomnia.¹ Paraneoplastic syndromes develop in approximately one of every 300 cancer patients, with an estimated incidence ranging between 1.6 and 8.9 cases per million person-years.^{1,15}

In MoS, 75% of cases test positive for CASPR2 antibodies, 60% for LGI1 antibodies, while smaller percentages present antibodies to netrin-1 or acetylcholine receptors. Thymoma is identified in 50–90% of cases.¹ The disease may be fatal in up to one-third of affected individuals, though a recent case series from India reported only one death among eight patients.⁷ The precise epidemiological profile of MoS remains unclear, as systematic studies are limited, suggesting the disorder is likely underdiagnosed and underreported.¹ A 2012 case series documented 29 patients,^{1,8} while another in 2021 included 14

additional cases.^{1,5} The majority of reports indicate a strong male predominance, with male-to-female ratios reported as high as 19:1 and ranging from 70% to 90% in other studies.⁴

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY

Antibodies against two VGKC-complex proteins CASPR2 and LGI1 are now strongly implicated in the pathogenesis of Morvan syndrome.^{1,10,16} Disorders associated with LGI1 antibodies typically present with limbic encephalitis, hyponatremia, REM sleep behaviour disorder, and faciobrachial dystonic seizures, whereas CASPR2 antibody-mediated conditions primarily involve peripheral nerve hyperexcitability.^{1,17,18,19}

CLINICAL PRESENTATION

CNS manifestations of MoS include encephalopathy, severe insomnia, vivid auditory hallucinations, delirium, confusion, amnesia, agitation, disorientation, and behavioural disturbances.^{1,4} Autonomic dysfunction (dysautonomia) manifests as instability with features such as excessive sweating, fever, palmoplantar erythema, pruritus, drooling, severe constipation, excessive lacrimation, cardiac arrhythmias, hypertension, weight loss, and sometimes hyponatremia due to the syndrome of inappropriate antidiuretic hormone secretion (SIADH).¹ Peripheral nervous system (PNS) involvement presents as nerve hyperexcitability with continuous muscle fiber activity, neuropathic pain, areflexia, and sensory deficits.^{1,7} Examples of central hyperactivity include confusion, cognitive impairment, hallucinations, insomnia, and myoclonus; autonomic hyperactivity may involve hyperhidrosis or blood pressure fluctuations; and peripheral hyperexcitability manifests as muscle cramps, myokymia, or neuromyotonia.⁸

DIAGNOSTIC EVALUATION

A definitive diagnosis of MoS is established by detecting elevated serum antibody titers for CASPR2 and LGI1. While VGKC antibody detection can indicate MoS, current recommendations emphasise testing specifically for CASPR2 and LGI1 rather than broad VGKC antibodies.¹ Routine investigations used in evaluating nervous system hyperexcitability such

as cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) analysis, brain MRI, electroencephalography (EEG), and positron emission tomography (PET) scans may be of limited diagnostic value, though they assist in excluding alternative diagnoses. Some imaging studies are employed to identify underlying malignancies.¹ Electromyography (EMG) can demonstrate myokymia; however, typical EMG findings in MoS include fasciculations, multiplets, and after-discharges, while true myokymia and neuromyotonia are less commonly recorded.^{1,20} Following antibody confirmation, imaging of the chest, abdomen, and pelvis via CT or PET scans is advised to screen for possible malignancy.¹

TREATMENT AND MANAGEMENT

Most published literature supports the effectiveness of immunomodulatory therapies, particularly plasmapheresis, in the treatment of Morvan syndrome.^{8,9,4} Therapeutic plasma exchange, often used in combination with immunosuppressive therapy, remains the preferred management strategy. Reported outcomes vary from full recovery to death, with mortality reaching 20% in a 2012 series by Irani et al.⁴ Plasma exchange is considered the most effective therapeutic option, though corticosteroids and other immunosuppressants are frequently co-administered.¹ Treatment regimens may include plasma exchange, intravenous immunoglobulin (IVIg), or long-term immunosuppression.² Patients have shown favourable responses to a range of immunotherapies, including corticosteroids, IVIg, plasmapheresis, azathioprine, cyclophosphamide,

rituximab, as well as symptomatic drugs such as carbamazepine, gabapentin, and clonazepam.⁴

PROGNOSIS

The clinical course of Morvan syndrome is highly variable, ranging from complete remission to fatal outcomes. Some patients may experience spontaneous recovery, though 20% mortality was reported in the 2012 series by Irani et al.¹ Prognosis remains unpredictable some patients recover completely, while others require prolonged care and ongoing management. The coexistence of thymoma with Morvan syndrome generally indicates a poorer prognosis.²

CASE SUMMARY

An 18-year-old female patient was admitted to general medicine with Chief complaints of acute lower back ache radiating to both lower limbs. The patient was apparently normal before 20 days, and after which she had complaints of LBA with B/L Sciatica with insidious onset and progressive in nature. H/O Insomnia for 20days.

Personal history:

Sleep Pattern was changed

Bowel and bladder habits were normal.

On Examination:

The patient was conscious and oriented.

Table 1: Vitals

BP	PR	RR	SPO2	Temp
120/70mmHg	88BPM	18CPM	98%@RA	97.2 F

On systemic examination: CVS: S1, S2 Heard, No murmur, RS: B/L AE + , P/A: Soft, non-tender, CNS: NFND

Table 2: Neurological Examination

		RIGHT	LEFT
TONE	UL	NORMAL	NORMAL
	LL	NORMAL	NORMAL
POWER	UL	5/5	5/5
	LL	5/5	5/5

DTR	UL	2+	2+
	LL	2+	2+
Plantar reflex		Flexion	Flexion

Hematology: In complete blood count, Hb-13.8g/dl, WBC-4170Cells/mm³, MCV-74.1fl, MCHC-24.5g/dl, RDW-CV-18.5, RDW-SD-46.6, Platelets-3.68lakh cells/mm³, CRP-4.9mg/l, APTT(test-25.13sec, control-31.2sec), PT(test-12.2sec, control-13.2sec) and INR-0.91.

Liver function test: Total bilirubin-0.5mg/dl, Direct Bilirubin-0.1mg/dl, Indirect bilirubin-0.4mg/dl, Total protein-8.1g/dl, Albumin-4.3g/dl, Globulin-3.8g/dl, Albumin/Globulin ratio-1.1, ALP-121.4U/l, SGOT-16.5U/L, SGPT-11.1U/L, and GGTP-28.4

Renal function test: eGFR-126.5 Urea-36.8mg/dl, Serum creatinine-0.7mg/dl and Uric acid-4.4mg/dl.

Biochemistry: Electrolytes (Sodium-136mEq/L, Pottasium-4.7mEq/L, Chloride-104mEq/L, Bicarbonate-23.5mEq/L and Calcium-8.1mg/dl), and RBS-155.8mg/dl, Blood group-B+ve, Vitamin B12-597pg/ml

Serology: HBsAg- -ve, HCV- Non-reactive, HIV I and II-Non-reactive

VGKC Antibody {CSF & Serum}:

Antibody to LGI 1 +Ve

Antibody to CASPR-2 + Ve

MRI whole spine with screening pelvis done

IMPRESSION:

Lumbar spine: Transitional lumbosacral junction with partial sacralization of L5 noted. Castellvi type II on the left side and type I on the right side L5/S1 disc is hypoplastic. L3/4 and L4/5 discs - small posterior bulges indenting the thecal sac. No major disc herniation or cauda equina compression seen.

Pelvis screening: Mild angulation is seen at the sacrococcygeal region, but no major marrow edema, subluxation or dislocation is seen. No marrow edema

or presacral fluid is seen. S1 joints appear intact; both hip joints are intact

Cervicothoracic spine: No signs of abnormal cord signal changes noted at present. No cord compression or cord edema seen. Clinical correlation and follow-up suggested

CT CHEST

No consolidation/no pleural effusion.

DIAGNOSIS

Morvan syndrome

TREATMENT

The patient was admitted for further evaluation and management. Patient was started on IV fluids, Inj. Tramadol 50mg TDS from day 1 to day 7; T. Paracetamol SR 1gm BD from day 1 to day 6; T. Pregabalin ER 75mg HS from day 1 to day 8; IV steroids (Inj. Methyl prednisolone sodium succinate 1gm in 500ml NS over 4 hours once daily from day 1 to day 6; Inj. Para 1gm SOS from day 1 to day 11; T. Phenytoin 100mg HS from day 1 to day 7; The patient was not passing stool for the past 2 days, T. Bisacodyl 10mg HS 5mg OD SOS from day 1 to day 10. After 2 days, VGKC antibody reports were received, which showed LGI-1 and CASPR-2 positive.

On day 3, right peripheral IV catheterization was done. A nephrologist's opinion was obtained for plasma pheresis. After prior preparation (IV Hydrocortisone sodium succinate 100mg STAT and IM Calcium gluconate 10ml STAT on day 3 is given. The patient underwent 5 cycles of plasma pheresis on alternate days from day 4 to day 13; T. Pregabalin ER 75mg changed to BD from day 9 to day 13; Inj. Tramadol 50mg changed to BD from day 8 to day 11; T. Pregabalin and nortriptyline Hcl combination 75/10mg BD from day 9 to day 12; Ointment Gabcica K was given on day 13; T. Tramadol Hcl and acetaminophen combination 37.5/325mg BD is given

on day 13; T. Cephalexin 150mg BD from day 12 to day 13. Meanwhile patient symptomatically improved. CT chest taken to R/O thymoma, whose reports revealed a normal study. The patient was discharged with the medications of T. Pregaba NT 75/10mg BD after food for 7 days; T. Ultra plus SOS after food for 5 days; T. Cephalexin 250 mg BD after food for 3 days; C. Pomerz BD after food for 7 days; T. Wysolone 20mg 3 tablets after breakfast for 7 days; T. Azathioprine 25mg OD after food for 7 days; T. Vonoprazan 20mg before breakfast OD for 7 days. The condition of the patient was stable at the time of discharge.

COURSE IN THE HOSPITAL

An 18-year-old female patient was admitted to the general medicine department with above mentioned complaints. Workup was done, which showed within normal limits, and VGKC antibody was sent. Patient was started on IV fluids, IV steroids, analgesics, neuro supportive therapy and other supportive care. After 5 days, VGKC antibody reports were received, which showed LGI-1 and CASPR-2 positive. A nephrologist's opinion was obtained for plasma pheresis. After prior preparation, the patient underwent 5 cycles of plasma pheresis on alternative days. Meanwhile patient symptomatically improved. CT chest taken to R/O thymoma, whose reports revealed a normal study. Over the 18 days of treatment patient symptomatically improved, no longer back backache or radiating pain. Hence, being discharged with the following medicines.

RESULTS

After 5 cycles of plasmapheresis and by other supportive treatments, the patient showed marked improvement in muscle fibrillation, insomnia, constipation, and other symptoms. No significant discomfort was reported thereafter. The most commonly used immunomodulatory therapy for this condition is plasmapheresis. In this patient, both CASPR2 and LGI1 antibodies were found to be positive.

DISCUSSION

Morvan's syndrome is primarily a clinical diagnosis, and a high index of suspicion is required to identify

this rare condition, especially when patients present with a combination of varied symptoms. This patient exhibited hyperexcitability involving the peripheral, autonomic, and central nervous systems. Insomnia, constipation, and neuromyotonia represented features of central hyperactivity, while painful cramps and myokymia, observed clinically and electrophysiologically, reflected peripheral motor hyperexcitability. The patient was seropositive for VGKC antibodies, including CASPR2 and LGI1. The most common CNS manifestation observed in this case was severe insomnia, a well-documented feature of Morvan's syndrome. Insomnia results from dysfunction involving the thalamus, hypothalamus, locus coeruleus, and raphe nuclei. These monoaminergic diencephalic and brainstem centres are crucial for maintaining arousal and autonomic balance, and disturbance in this homeostasis leads to insomnia. In fatal familial insomnia, there is progressive thalamic degeneration, whereas in Morvan's syndrome, the dysfunction is reversible and related to VGKC antibody activity. Although seizures are uncommon in Morvan's syndrome, they can occur in the early or acute phase or a few months before diagnosis. In this patient, MRI brain (performed to rule out autoimmune limbic encephalitis) and thoracic MRI (to exclude thymoma) were normal. MRI of the whole spine and pelvis showed only mild changes. CSF analysis revealed positive VGKC antibodies (CASPR2 and LGI1), confirming antibody-mediated pathology. Alterations in VGKC antibodies can produce a wide range of symptoms, from headaches to seizures. Among these, CASPR2 and LGI1 antibodies play the most important roles. In this case, both antibodies were positive, and motor hyperactivity was manifested as neuromyotonia and myokymia. The course of Morvan's syndrome varies from spontaneous remission to fatal progression. In this patient, several features were due to central nervous system involvement, though peripheral and autonomic disturbances also contributed. The relationship between the wide range of symptoms and antibody mechanisms remains not fully understood. Thymoma, commonly associated with Morvan's syndrome, was excluded in this case through imaging. Like other autoimmune or paraneoplastic conditions, Morvan's syndrome responds to IVIg, plasma exchange, and immunosuppressive therapy. The prognosis is usually poorer when thymoma is present.

Five days of admission, the VGKC antibody report confirmed LGI1 and CASPR2 positivity. Based on the nephrologist's recommendation, the patient underwent five alternate-day cycles of plasma exchange after appropriate preparation. The patient showed symptomatic improvement following the procedure. CT chest ruled out thymoma. The patient continued to improve with prednisolone therapy and plasmapheresis. Considering the wide range of clinical and psychiatric features, Morvan's syndrome can mimic several other neurological disorders. Hence, a high level of clinical suspicion is necessary for early diagnosis and appropriate management.

TAKE-HOME POINTS

Morvan's syndrome is characterised by central, autonomic, and peripheral hyperexcitability, commonly due to CASPR2 antibody involvement. Autonomic function tests show dysfunction in around half of the patients, while others may exhibit orthostatic hypotension, early autonomic dysfunction, or postural orthostatic tachycardia syndrome. Polysomnography (PSG) findings include insomnia, lack of deep sleep, high-frequency beta activity, REM behaviour disorder, and periodic leg movements. Neuropsychological testing often reveals subtle involvement of the left frontal and temporal lobes. Most patients respond favourably to corticosteroid therapy.

CONCLUSION

The etiology and clinical severity of Morvan syndrome remain poorly understood. The condition has been linked to antibodies directed against voltage-gated potassium channel complexes, particularly contactin-associated protein-like 2 (CASPR2) and leucine-rich glioma inactivated protein 1 (LGI1). LGI1 antibodies are typically associated with seizures, amnesia, confusion, hyponatremia, and a relatively favourable prognosis, whereas CASPR2 antibodies are more frequently linked to peripheral nervous system involvement, a potential association with tumours, and poorer outcomes. Patients have demonstrated varying responses to immunotherapeutic agents such as corticosteroids, intravenous immunoglobulins, plasma exchange, azathioprine, cyclophosphamide, and rituximab, as well as symptomatic therapies including

carbamazepine, gabapentin, and clonazepam. However, no definitive long-term cure has been established to date. Thymoma occurs in nearly half of reported cases, and thymectomy may be curative, as illustrated in our patient. In summary, we describe an atypical presentation of Morvan syndrome in a female patient positive for VGKC antibodies. A high index of clinical suspicion is crucial, as the symptom profile of Morvan syndrome is heterogeneous and lacks a pathognomonic feature. This unique presentation underscores the importance of continued research to elucidate disease mechanisms, refine diagnostic criteria, and optimise management strategies for this rare and unpredictable autoimmune disorder.

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HOW TO CITE: Afsea A*, Mohamed Rabeek S, Lakshmanan M, Rubina Sajjath O, Nandha Kumar S, An Indian female Morvan patient with LGI1 and CASPR2 antibodies: A Rare case report, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2025,1(12), 100-106. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17778065>

